

ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS: EXPLORING PROBIOTIC PROPERTIES IN VEGETABLE PRODUCTS

Brîndușa Covaci, Mihai Covaci, Centre for Mountain Economy & Zealandina Agency, United Kingdom & Australia

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Abstract

This article undertakes a comprehensive synthesis of select vegetable products indigenous to the mountainous regions of Romania, specifically focusing on onion (*Allium cepa*) and the natural juices derived from apples (*Malus pumila*) and pears (*Pyrus communis*). The primary objective of this investigation is to underscore that these products, characterized by their elevated nutritional profiles and inherent probiotic properties, constitute staples widely utilized in Romania. Entrepreneurs situated in the Romanian mountainous regions, specializing in vegetable products, accentuate the pivotal role of these items in their commercial enterprises. The preliminary insights for this study were extracted from the official websites of mountain producers, while the statistical data were sourced from the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products.

Keywords: mountain entrepreneurs, natural probiotic, vegetable products

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M.C. – conceptualization; B.C. – conceptualization and final

The *Allium cepa*, commonly known as onion and classified under plant products by OECD (2019), exhibits a round or elongated shape and is available in white, red, or yellow varieties. Onions are versatile, existing in fresh, dried, semi-dried, or green forms. Fruit juice, categorized as a vegetable product by FAO (2005), is characterized as an unfermented yet fermentable liquid derived from the edible portion of ripe and fresh fruit, or fruit preserved in a healthy state, even post-harvest, through treatments compliant with Codex Alimentarius Commission regulations.

In Romania, *Allium cepa*, particularly in its green or dried forms, stands out as the most consumed variant, with 56 mountain producers documented in the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products (RNPM) as of September 21, 2021. A regional breakdown reveals representation from various counties, including Argeş, Cluj, Hunedoara, Mureş, and Timiş, each contributing one producer. Additionally, Bacău, Caraş, Sibiu, and Suceava have two producers each, while Gorj and Satu Mare host three producers. Notably, Maramureş boasts seven producers, Vâlcea has nine, and Covasna leads with 18. Out of the 329 mountain producers specializing in probiotic plant products, 56 are dedicated to onions, constituting a substantial 17.02% share within this entrepreneur class.

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Figure 1. Mountain producers and related assortments of allium cepa (onions) from Romania

Source: National Agency for Mountain Areas (2021), National Register of Mountain Products

Natural juices, specifically those derived from apples (*Malus pumila*) and pears (*Pyrus communis*), serve as an apt medium for incorporating *Lactobacillus paracasei* as a probiotic, as highlighted in research by Pimentel et al. (2015). Over the storage period, studies indicate a notable increase in the viable cell count in apples due to their sucrose content. Notably, unfermented juice experienced a higher loss of ascorbic acid (40%) compared to fermented juice (23%). This trend was consistent for antioxidant activity and polyphenolic compounds, endowing the functional Mountain Perspective Journal (2/2021)

food with enhanced nutritional benefits (Pereira et al., 2013). Apple juice, when subjected to fermentation with *Lactobacillus plantarum* PCS26, results in a functional beverage characterized by high sensory acceptance and a promising shelf life (Dimitrovski, 2015). Meanwhile, Changchong pear juice demonstrated efficacy in promoting growth and enhancing survival for the *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* ST-III strain and other probiotic representatives of this species, as demonstrated by Yan et al. (2021).

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The escalating demand for functional foods and probiotics surpasses that of traditional dairy products, prompting continuous efforts in product development. Panda et al.'s (2017) study, centered on the preparation technology and characteristics of lactic acid-fermented juice using prick pear (*Opuntia* sp.), underscores this trend. Moreover, research findings indicate that *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG, sourced from pears, exhibits the capability to control the growth of *Salmonella* and *L. monocytogenes* on freshly cut pears (Iglesias et al., 2017).

As per the Romanian National Register of Mountain Products (RNPM) dated September 21, 2021, natural apple (SM) and pear (SP) juices, originating from 11 producers, are available in the market. These include two producers from Caraș-Severin specializing in pear juice, and eight

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producers from Caraş-Severin, Bacău, Dâmboviţa, Harghita, Maramureş, Sibiu, Vâlcea, each contributing to the apple juice category. Additionally, one producer from Caraş-Severin offers a mix of apple and pear juice (SMP). Notably, among the 329 mountain producers of vegetable products, only 11 are engaged in the production of apple and pear juice, constituting a modest 3.34% of the total.

Figure 3.5. Mountain producers of apple and pear juices from Romania

Source: National Agency for Mountain Areas (2021), National Register of Mountain Products

The prevalence of allium cepa (onion) and apple/pear juices among the overall producers and assortments of mountain products in Romania remains modest. In contrast, numerous European countries beyond Central and Eastern Europe, as well as other global nations, exhibit significantly

higher proportions in the production and consumption of onion/apple/pear juices. To foster the growth of the plant sector, particularly focusing on potent natural probiotics like *allium sativum* (garlic), as well as apple and pear juices, it is imperative for both public and private governance in Romania to enact essential measures.

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